

Report on the outcomes of a Short-Term Scientific Mission¹

Action number: CA22132

Grantee name: Anthony R Thornton

Details of the STSM

Title: STSM between MercuryDPM and preCICE team

Start and end date: 13/09/2025 to 01/10/2025

Description of the work carried out during the STSM

Description of the activities carried out during the STSM. Any deviations from the initial working plan shall also be described in this section.

(max. 500 words)

The aim of this STSM was to advance the CFD-DEM benchmarking activities within the ON-DEM network, focusing on preCICE-based coupling. A major outcome was the definition and inclusion of four new benchmarks in the ON-DEM suite:

1. Segregation in a fluid-saturated rotating drum, capturing particle-fluid interactions during rotational segregation.
2. Sedimentation of a constant porosity block, examining settling behaviour under gravity.
3. Granular Rayleigh-Taylor instability, studying density-driven instabilities in granular-fluid systems.
4. Fluidised bed, characterising the dynamics of fluidised particulate systems.

These benchmarks complement and extend the existing suite, which was reviewed to ensure consistency and clarity. Concurrently, the CFD-DEM benchmarking page on the ON-DEM wiki was reorganised and updated, providing a clearer overview of benchmarks and methodologies.

The benchmarking exercise was expanded to include additional CFD-DEM codes. Beyond previously involved tools, four new codes were integrated: LIGGGHTS-PreCICE-OpenFOAM, Mercury-PreCICE-OpenFOAM, Moomph (Mercury-oomphlib), and MercuryDPM (SPH-DEM). Integration involved detailed discussions with developers to understand coupling strategies, capabilities, and validation procedures. Several remote meetings were conducted, and an additionally visit to Munich to meet in person with Tom Scrase, lead of Moomph CFD development, was added to

¹ This report is submitted by the grantee to the Action MC for approval and for claiming payment of the awarded grant. The Grant Awarding Coordinator coordinates the evaluation of this report on behalf of the Action MC and instructs the GH for payment of the Grant.

STSM. This was in addition, to the visit to Stuttgart originally planned. This meeting facilitated alignment on coupling practices and benchmark implementation.

In the middle of the STSM, participation at the PARTEC and POWTECH conferences in Nuremberg provided valuable exposure to recent advances in particulate and multiphase simulations and opportunities for networking and collaboration. Additionally, I visited the University of Twente to discuss the emerging SPH-based CFD-DEM coupling being developed there, broadening the benchmarking exercise's scope.

Beyond benchmark definition and code integration, significant effort was dedicated to improving documentation and tutorials. Mercury-PreCICE-OpenFOAM and Moomph CFD-DEM tutorials were clarified and reorganised, ensuring accessibility for new users and reproducibility of benchmark results. This work supports ON-DEM's mission to provide open, transparent, and well-documented simulation tools for the community.

In summary, this STSM strengthened the ON-DEM CFD-DEM benchmarking framework through four new benchmarks, integration of additional codes, review of existing benchmarks, and enhanced documentation. These outcomes improve reproducibility, accessibility, and visibility of CFD-DEM benchmarks within the preCICE community, providing a solid foundation for future collaborative development and research.

Description of the STSM main achievements and planned follow-up activities

This Short-Term Scientific Mission (STSM) successfully achieved its primary objectives, addressing all six planned milestones and contributing significantly to the ON-DEM Action goals of promoting openness, interoperability, and reproducibility in CFD-DEM coupling. Three milestones (1, 4, 5) are complete, two (2, 3) are at first-draft stage, and one (6) is ongoing.

Milestone 1 – Finalisation of preCICE Coupling Implementation

This milestone was fully achieved. The MercuryDPM-preCICE coupling was finalised, tested, and merged into the main MercuryDPM repository, making it openly available to the community. Collaboration with preCICE core developers ensured adherence to best practices and a robust integration pathway for future development.

Milestones 2 & 3 – Tutorials and Documentation

Initial tutorials and documentation were created to guide users through typical MercuryDPM-preCICE workflows, including examples of fluid-particle interaction cases. These materials, which cover both Mercury-preCICE-OpenFOAM and Moomph CFD-DEM coupling examples, are now available. The documentation provides setup guidance, configuration examples, and reproducible test cases. While the essential tutorials are complete, both the MercuryDPM and preCICE documentation will continue to be expanded and refined to improve accessibility and ease of adoption.

Milestones 4 & 5 – Peer Review, Code Quality Assurance, and Release

Extensive interaction with developers of related CFD-DEM coupling codes—LIGGGHTS-preCICE-OpenFOAM, Mercury-preCICE-OpenFOAM, Moomph (Mercury-oomphlib), and MercuryDPM (SPH-DEM)—helped align testing approaches and strengthen code quality standards across platforms. Informal peer review and internal testing confirmed the stability of the MercuryDPM-preCICE coupling. With the successful merge into the main branch, the code is now part of the official MercuryDPM release cycle, with automated testing planned to maintain long-term robustness and reliability.

Milestone 6 – Execution of ON-DEM CFD-DEM Benchmark Simulations

A key achievement of the STSM was the definition and inclusion of four new benchmarks within the ON-DEM framework:

1. Segregation in a fluid-saturated rotating drum
2. Sedimentation of a constant porosity block
3. Granular Rayleigh-Taylor instability

4. Fluidised bed

These new cases complement the three existing benchmarks, which were reviewed and updated for clarity and consistency. The ON-DEM CFD–DEM benchmarking page was reorganised and cleaned, improving accessibility and transparency. Several remote discussions and an in-person meeting with Moomph CFD lead Tom Scrase in Munich further supported alignment of benchmark implementations.

Assessment and Planned Follow-up

Overall, the STSM achieved its planned goals and produced all expected outcomes. The MercuryDPM–preCICE coupling is now publicly available, supported by tutorials and documentation, and underpinned by a well-defined benchmarking framework. The next steps will focus on improving documentation on both the MercuryDPM and preCICE websites, publicising its availability, and implementing the new benchmarks to compare results across the different coupling frameworks. These collaborative studies will validate the coupling, establish best practices, and lead to future joint publications and coordinated development efforts.